

Preprint posting checklist

A short checklist to help you
maximise the benefits of posting a
preprint.

Preprint posting checklist

The following is a detailed checklist for posting a preprint. This will ensure that your preprint is as high quality as possible and that you maximise the benefits of preprinting.

Scientific readiness

Prior to posting your preprint, the first step is to ensure that your work is ready for public sharing.

- Main research question is clearly stated
- Methods are described in sufficient detail for evaluation and re-use
- Results support the conclusions and are free from hyperbolic language
- Limitations are explicitly discussed
- Key claims are supported by data or citations
- Figures and tables are complete and legible
- Statistical analyses have been checked
- All references are complete and accurate
- You've incorporated private feedback from colleagues and co-authors

Writing and Presentation

Clear writing and presentation of your work helps reuse and improves impact.

- Title accurately reflects findings
- Abstract is concise and balanced
- Figures have informative captions
- Acronyms defined on first use
- Grammar and formatting reviewed

AI/LLM use

- Any LLM generated text has been checked by a human for accuracy
- Any LLM generated content is free from hallucinations or delusions
- LLM use has been declared within the manuscript

Co-author approval

It is essential that all co-authors approve the manuscript and agree to post a preprint. Failure to do so can result in withdrawal of the preprint.

- All authors have reviewed the manuscript
- Author order has been agreed upon
- Corresponding author identified and current contact information present
- Author affiliations are current and correct

- ORCID IDs included
- All authors approve public release as a preprint
- All authors have agreed on which preprint server to use

Ethics and compliance

All research should be conducted ethically and in-line with any legal, institutional or funder requirements.

- Human-subjects approvals documented
- Animal-study approvals documented
- Informed consent requirements satisfied
- Privacy-sensitive information removed
- Data sharing complies with regulations and institutional/funder policies
- Funding sources disclosed
- Conflicts of interest disclosed

Data and Code

Ensuring that any data or code is clear, well documented and available is essential for reproducibility and trust of your work.

- Data availability statement included
- Code availability statement included
- External data or code links are included
- Links to repositories tested and all resolve
- Data in repositories is accessible to the public
- Software versions documented
- Supplementary materials prepared and included

Journal Compatibility

The overwhelming majority of journals accept preprints. However, if you're submitting to a small or more niche journal it may be worth checking the policies to ensure that preprints are acceptable.

- Checked your target journal's policy using the [Open Policy Finder](#)

Risk Assessment

Performing a risk assessment ensures that your work is more difficult to mis-use or mis-interpret.

- Findings are not overstated
- Potential misuse or misinterpretation of data and conclusions considered
- Press or media communication plan discussed (if applicable) and is appropriate

- High-impact claims have received extra internal review

Final Decision

- If this preprint became public today, we would be comfortable defending its main claims, methods, and limitations.

Preprint Server Submission

There are many considerations when selecting which server to submit your preprint to and when to submit. We have further guidance on this available from the Rippling Ideas [YouTube](#) channel and resources within [Zenodo](#).

- Appropriate preprint server selected
- Time of posting agreed upon by co-authors
- PDF renders correctly, without mistakes
- Source/Supplementary files uploaded if required
- Subject categories selected
- License selected intentionally
- Abstract copied correctly into submission form
- Author information entered correctly
- Final preview reviewed before submission

Post-Preprinting Plan

Having a strong post-preprinting plan helps you to maximise the attention your preprint may receive. This can also help with subsequent journal submission and may even result in editors inviting you to submit.

- Team notified when preprint goes live
- DOI or identifier recorded
- Research profiles updated
- Feedback collection plan established
- Social media thread posted
- Version update process agreed upon
- Journal submission timeline defined

Updates to the preprint

A key benefit to posting a preprint is that you can update it at any time. This mechanism can be used to add new data and “iterate” a story or in response to feedback.

- Changes between versions have been described and included
- All coauthors have reviewed the revised version
- All coauthors approve the update

- Data repositories have been updated if needed
- Code repositories reflect the current analyses
- Links, DOIs, and repository references have been checked
- Major corrections are disclosed transparently
- Any withdrawn claims are explicitly identified
- Any newly recognized limitations are discussed
- Updated versions are shared on social media

Congratulations

Congratulations on posting your preprint! This is a huge milestone in any scientific endeavour and you should take time to celebrate. Here's one final, but essential, checklist.

- Thank the co-authors and any colleagues who provided advice and feedback for their effort and work
 - Particularly recognise students and support staff who often go unrecognised
- Take time to enjoy the feeling of moving the work from "in preparation" to "publicly available" before moving onto the next project
- Celebrate with colleagues in whatever form is customary: coffee, cake, lunch, drinks, or a dedicated Preprint Posting Party™

Useful templates

Version Summary Template

Before uploading a revised preprint, prepare a brief summary to help readers identify what changed between versions. Some preprint servers have dedicated forms for this information but when this is not available, a supplemental file or direct inclusion into the manuscript is advised. You may upload a revised preprint in response to private feedback, preprint peer review or because you have developed additional data or uncovered mistakes.

The following is a template for version changes. Purple highlights indicate important information to include:

Version [X] ([DATE]): Added validation experiments on Dataset B, corrected a preprocessing error affecting Figure 4, updated statistical analyses, expanded discussion of limitations, and revised conclusions regarding model generalizability.

Limitation Statement Template

Including a genuine limitations statement can help increase trust in your work and also qualify your findings and conclusions. Such a statement should not be used to describe limitations and how they were overcome but to describe true and standing limitations. Where possible, include citations to support your statements. For example, in metascience many studies use databases that are known to have limitations and missing data. A limitations

statement would state that this is a known issue with these databases that could impact or restrict the conclusions. A strong limitations section typically answers the question: "Under what circumstances should readers be cautious about applying or interpreting these findings?" rather than simply listing weaknesses.

Template:

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings.

Scope and generalizability. The study was conducted using [population, dataset, setting, or database], which may limit the generalizability of the results to [other populations, datasets, settings, or domains].

Data limitations. The analysis relies on [data source], which may contain [missing values, measurement errors, reporting biases, sampling biases, etc.]. These factors could influence the observed results.

Methodological limitations. The study uses [method/model/experimental design], which involves assumptions such as [assumptions]. If these assumptions are violated, the estimated effects or conclusions may differ.

Causal interpretation. Because [observational data/non-randomized design/other constraint] was used, the findings should be interpreted as [associational/correlational] rather than strictly causal.

Evaluation limitations. Performance was evaluated using [metrics and benchmarks]. Alternative metrics, datasets, or real-world deployment conditions may yield different results.

Uncertainty and future work. Additional research is needed to evaluate [open questions], test the findings in [new settings], and assess the robustness of the conclusions under different conditions.

Despite these limitations, the study provides evidence that [main contribution] and establishes a foundation for future investigation.

Useful resources

- [A new PI's guide to promoting open science and preprints in your lab](#)
- [Getting started on BlueSky: a guide for scientists](#)
- [State of Preprints in the Life Sciences](#)

Contact & further info

In 2024 we founded [Rippling Ideas](#), an organisation dedicated to advancing preprint adoption, fostering trust in research and improving the culture of academia. This is achieved through advocacy, training and communication. Learn more through our [YouTube](#) page or [Zenodo](#) repository.

Contact: jonny.coates@ripplingideas.org

Licence

This report may be re-used and is provided under a CC-BY-SA licence.

Rippling Ideas

Turning ideas into waves